

TERMS OF TEXT PROBLEMS TO STUDENTS SOME CHARACTERISTIC OF UNDERSTANDING

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Annotation. In this article, some features of students' conscious mastering of the terms of text problems, the most important stages of problem solving are described, and two problems are mentioned.

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Problem solving plays a very important role in teaching mathematics. Because the purpose of problem solving is the students' theoretical knowledge consciously fast and rigorous application in the field of solving practical problems is to teach to do.

Problem solving is the application of mathematical theory in practice. How great is the pedagogical significance of problem solving in teaching mathematics that the teacher is planning his work as well as during teaching how much attention should be paid is well understood from what has been said.

Various mathematical concepts are created by solving problems are often some is the basis for deriving theoretical rules. The problem is the teacher's math helps to enrich and develop speech. Issues are different facts of life helps to understand quantitative relationships between. Appropriate content issues are a tool for educating students in the spirit of patriotism will be in the growth of students' logical thinking, their quantities problems in determining the connections between them, making correct conclusions is especially important.

And especially teaching to solve problems in the 5-6 grade mathematics course through, the growth of students' logical thinking, the knowledge gained during this period, study skills future algebra and geometry course study to also mature in the field of mathematics in the future of students will be the basis for them to become specialists.

Solving the given complex problem is relevant and attention of the students knowledge should be involved (sometimes to solve the problem, for example the use of knowledge obtained from nature, literature and similar subjects is required will be done; from the connection or similarly of the matter to another familiar matter should be used).

The most important steps in solving text problems are as follows:

- 1) learning and mastering the condition of the issue;
- 2) write the condition of the issue;
- 3) analytical-synthetic analysis;
- 4) write a solution to the problem based on the questions or an explanatory solution;
- 5) check the solution;
- 6) work on the issue after it is resolved;

Each of these steps is important if teachers think about it seriously eases the solution process and helps to understand the problem.

Students to read expressively, piece, consciously it takes getting used to.

Understanding the content of the problem is the key to solving the problem is a step. As you know from the school mathematics course, some students are textual they have a lot of difficulties in working with the problems listed above students can fully solve the problem with the help of the passed steps will be.

Determining the relationship between the given and sought quantities in the condition, which information is missing or which of them is hidden in the condition opening the given, the first step of solving the problem – the condition of the problem will be learning (this is sometimes called analyzing the condition of the problem).

Studying the condition of the problem begins with its careful reading, then the content of the issue and the question are defined.

Readers often imagine the real facts presented in the problem as a result of his lack of knowledge, he finds it difficult to solve the problem; sometimes in a matter condition does not understand the terms used. Some terms and concepts the meaning should be explained by the teacher himself, for this purpose, he is simple uses issues.

Clarrification of the content of the problem, the quantities given in the problem determining the connections between them, writing the condition of the problem in the form of a scheme allow a you to get The more successful this scheme is, the more it solves making a plan becomes easier in most cases.

Suffisient assessment to briefly outline the terms of the problem failure to do so will damage the accuracy of perception. Briefly, the terms of the matter the importance of writing is especially that it helps to understand the issue helps to think and understand. The first condition is perception if not, the connections between quantities, some parts of the condition compare and contrast cannot be understood. Especially difficult issues it is very important to write the terms briefly. Experience has shown that the best students, and even teachers themselves, in solving difficult problems they use shorthand writing of terms.

Problem 1. 10.5 kg of pears, 15.2 kg apples and 8.5 kg of plums were mixed. The whole mixture costs 2,830,000 soums. 1kg pear 1 kg without 3,200 soums are expensive, and 1 kg of apples is 2,000 soums more expensive than 1 kg of plums find the value of 1kg of each fruit in the mixture.

10.5 kg of pears	1kg pear 1 kg from apple	all mixed
15.2 kg of apples	3200 soums is expensive	2833600 soums
8.5 kg of plums	1 kg of apples 1 kg from plums 2000 soums is expensive	

Write the condition of the problem:

How much does a kilogram of each fruit cost?

If the condition of the issues can be graphically illustrated, it is the opportunity should be used effectively. A condition represented by a graph is usually will be very fluent.

Problem 2. The collective farm planted beets on three plots of land. Everything into 967.46 ha. Plot II is 26.4 less than I and 58 less than III. How many hectares is each plot?

Let's express the condition graphically:

Graphical images make problem solving easier. That's why it is the problem can be drawn as follows:

From this drawing, 964.46 from the three of area II and again $26.4+58=84.4$. It is seen that it is formed from (ha).

How the way to solve the problem becomes much easier.

The next part of studying the condition of the matter is thinking based on analytical way (analysis) or synthesis way (synthesis).

In the process of analything the problem: what quantities are shown in the problem, what are the connections between them, what to find, where and how to find in order to answer the question of the problem, you need to work in what order we should pay attention to the question that we should go. Analytical in analysis it is especially important to use the method.

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